

SEVENTH BHAVA AND MARRIAGE

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Abstract:

Houses in Sanskrit are referred to as 'bhava' meaning a mode of being, essence or feeling, and are thus, in Vedic Astrology, a changing twelfold division of the zodiac circle, which depend upon the position of the earth in its daily rotation relative to the heaven. As the earth rotates during the course of the day, the whole zodiac gradually rises in the East and sets in the West. The tenth house is the zodiac sign which is exactly on the top (the north direction) at the time of birth. Significance of the Seventh house and the impacts created by the planetary position in the horoscope for a person's marriage life is analysed in this article.

Key Words: Zodiac Sign, Planets, Early or Delay Marriage, Seventh Bhava, Child birth, Natives, Cusp.

Introduction:

The point rising in the East at the time of the birth is known as the Ascendant, the most important single consideration used in Vedic Astrology for predictions. The Zodiac sign which includes the Ascendant is considered as the first house. There are twelve houses in an Astrology chart, each of which defines a specific domain or area of our action in life. The sign next to the ascendant (which will rise the next) becomes the second house and so on. The tenth house is the zodiac sign which is exactly on the top (the north direction) at the time of birth. Seventh House plays a major role in a person's marriage life. Planetary positions in the Seventh Bhava also plays a vital role for deciding the time of marriage and the appearance of the partner and the understanding towards each other.

The purpose and the division of the Zodiac:

The ancient Hindu way of life, based on the Karma theory, looked at the progress of the human soul based on three essential macroscopic parameters. They are: The Karma acquired from the person's past life, the karma the person acquires by virtue of the person's actions in his present life and based on these his future life. They classified a person's present life into four broad aspects. Dharma or right living, Artha or the monetary aspect, Kama or the desires and finally Moksha or spiritual progress and liberation.

They recognized the importance of balancing these four aspects of life for the proper progress. To understand and improve all these four aspects they gave us various Shastras. The Veda shastras for spiritual progress, the Dharma and Nyaya shastras for the legal and social conduct, the Artha (finance), Ganita (mathematics), Vanijya (trade) shastras for earning money, Sangeeta (music), Nritya (dance), Shilpa (art), Paka (cooking) shastras for pleasure. Finally, the Jyotishya (Jyoti=light+ Isha=God meaning the light of God to remove ignorance) was given to us as a guide, to get the best results during the most suitable times, in each of the above four areas of life. The entire basis and theology of our Astrology is based on these principles.

Explanation of Bhava:

The Bhavas as per Brighusutra Significations of the Twelve Houses of the Horoscope. The sage Brigu explains the Bhavas in his Brighusutra as under.

First House (or Lagna-Ascendant):

The first house or Lagna represent Physical stature, colour, form and shape, constitution, health, vitality and vigour, natural dispositions and tendencies, personality and struggle for life, honour, dignity, prosperity, general well-being, head, upper part of the face, virtues, longevity, start in life and an idea about the general structure of life.

Second House:

Money matters, fortune, profit, gain or loss, one's power and resources, worldly attainments and possession of extrinsic value, jewellery, precious stones, bonds, securities and shares, speech, vision, right eye, memory, imagination, nails, tongue, nose, teeth, chin, family members. This is also a house of death or marakasthan. Many scholars believe that education is also a signification of this house.

Third House:

Mental inclination, ability, memory, intellect, inclination to study, courage, firmness, valour, prowess, heroism, the person's brothers or sisters, cousins, neighbours, short travels, communications such as railways, wireless, posts and telegraphs, correspondence, writings, change of residence, signing contracts or agreements, rumours, carrying tales, hands, throat, shoulder blade, collarbone, arms nervous system.

Fourth House:

Mother, one's home (native place), residence, domestic environments, grave yard, private affairs, secret life, vehicles, fields, pastures, farms, orchards, mines, buildings, ancestral property, hidden treasure, academic education, wells, water, milk, rivers, lakes etc.

Fifth House:

Progeny (children), inclinations, pleasure, artistic talent, recreation, amusement, sports, romance, competitive activities like cards, crosswords, lottery, gambling or betting, love affairs, ambassadors, the good and the bad, mantra-tantra, religious mindedness, high learning and wisdom, intelligence, enormous riches, spiritual practice etc.

Sixth House:

Sickness, diseases, nursing, food, service, employees, servants, debts, cattle, tenants, enemies, miserliness, intense anguish, litigation, maternal uncle etc.

Seventh House:

House of union or earthly ties, legal bondage, partner in life (wife or husband), partner in business, conjugal life, influence in foreign countries and reputation achieved there, sexual life, marital relations, danger to life, marakasthanam (house of death).

Eighth House:

Longevity or span of life, also called house of death (because end of longevity is death), inheritance, legacies, wills, insurance, pension and gratuity, accidents, death by drowning, fire or suicide; misery, misfortune, sorrow, strife, worries, disgrace, delay, dejection, disappointment, defeat, loss and obstruction, theft, robbery, chronic diseases.

Ninth House:

Faith, wisdom and divine worship, fortune or luck (bhagyam), philosophy, religious and philosophical beliefs, meditation, intuition and forethought, places of worship, sacrifices and charity, father, preceptor (Guru), teaching, Dhana, grandchildren, dreams and visions, knees, communication with spirits, long journeys, voyage, air travel, higher education, foreign travel.

Tenth House:

Thighs, honour, dignity, public esteem, name and fame, power, prestige, credit (for good work and conduct), success and status, rank and renown, respect and reputation, ambition and authority, worldly activities, responsibilities, permanency (in service), promotion, advancement, appointment, profession, last rites to one's parents, religious functions. Government, high position such as President, Prime Minister or Minister, pilgrimage to holy places, honour from Government.

Eleventh House:

Friends, society, community, favourites, ambitions, wishes, desires and their fulfilment, gains of wealth, success in undertakings, incoming wealth, profits, prosperity, elder brothers and sisters, recovery from illness, dawn of fortune, ankles.

Twelfth House:

Loss and impediments, restraint and limitation, waste and extravagance, expenses, drudgery and deception, investments, donations, charities, separation from family, going to faraway places, sorrow and sin, misery and misfortune, poverty, imprisonment, secret enemies, confinement in hospital, association, fraud, scandal, disgrace, secret sorrows, success through occult affairs, the feet, the left eye, the left ear, comforts of bed, debts, life in a foreign place and Moksha (final salvation).

The Birth Chart is the celestial canvas of the sky at the moment of a person's birth. It is divided into twelve houses which is an accommodation of nine planets, also known as Bhava. It is filled with many cosmic symbols that represent the past, present and future of the person's life.

About Seventh House in Vedic Astrology:

The Seventh House is considered the House of Partnerships, marriage being the most important of them all. It is also called the House of Marriage. All the previous houses (one to six) were focused on self and individual. But now the focus shifts from 'self' to 'others', which involves partnerships. Everything related to marriage is ruled by this house.

The position of planets in the Seventh House in Rasi governs attraction for the opposite sex, desire to have a partner, sexual fantasies, commitment, passion and possessiveness. This house reveals why the person indulge in a relationship - is it for love, money, practical reasons, social pressure or to fill a void in his personal life. It also indicates the person's progeny.

The Seventh House (also known as House of Descendant) is the exact opposite of First House (also known as House of Ascendant). Together they complement each other. The Seventh House represents what the person is looking for.

The House of Descendant (Seventh House) sits directly across the House of Ascendant (First House). While the First house indicates longevity, the Seventh house opposes and poses a threat to longevity.

Fundamentals of Seventh House in Rasi:

- Vedic name : Kalathra Bhava or Pathni Bhava
- Natural Ruling Planet and Sign : Venus and Libra
- Body parts associated : Kidneys, lower back, lower pelvic area
- People in Seventh House : Romantic partners and other people we are in partnerships with
- Activities in Seventh House : Sexual relations, business negotiations, diplomacy, enjoyable conversations with others, debates and tolerance.

Meaning of Seventh House:

Seventh house is related to the partnership and represents the relationship with others. The seventh house in Astrology signifies a married relationship with others. With the help of the seventh house, we can study how we influence the special person in our lives and how that person influences us. The seventh house in astrology is governed by the sign Libra and ruled by the planet Venus.

The Signs and Planets associated with the Seventh House:

The Seventh house is also known as Kalathra Bhava in Vedic Astrology and is ruled by the Libra sign. Planet Venus is the natural significator of the Seventh house in Vedic astrology. The Seventh house is a weak house for Jupiter and Sun. But is the best house for Moon, Mars, Mercury, Venus and Saturn.

The areas of life ruled and governed by the Seventh House:

The Seventh house influences things between the person and his life partner and other partners (like business partners and so on). Thus, attraction to the opposite gender, the need for commitment in a relationship, shades of passion, physical intimacy and related fantasies, level of understanding, all these are governed by the Seventh house compatibility. The body parts influenced by the Seventh house include kidney and lower back. So, the Seventh house has lots in it for our relationships. And relationships are really very important in our life. Because it is the relationships that connect us to the people around us and everyone in this world. And what lies at the core of our relationship is marriage. As the Seventh house impacts our marriage in a big way, so it is bound to influence our happiness or the lack of it in a very substantial manner.

The Seventh House also Influences Childbirth Issues:

Besides, the Seventh house in Rasi is about the person's willingness to have children. It also deals with issues like problems and disinterest in carnal fulfilment, problems in the reproductive system, infertility and progeny problems. The Seventh house also points to the reason why we take an interest in a partnership. Is it because of love, money, social pressure or any other reason.

The Significance of the Seventh House:

Individual's partner and marriage are ruled by seventh house. With the help of seventh house, we can easily find out the character of another person and how we build a relationship with our loved one. Seventh house also focuses on the dark side of our unions such as divorce, lawsuits and treaties, which all fall within this house. Besides the close relationships and marriage, business partnerships are also a crucial part of the seventh house including Career bonds, agreements, contracts, lawsuits, and legal issues.

The Seventh house is also about cooperation and adjusting. Because it is what a person needs the most while dealing with his partner. The success in his professional & business partnerships also depends on the situation prevailing in the Seventh house. The equation which he shares with his business partners and others who are close to him professionally is bound to influence his success.

The movements in the Seventh house in horoscope can also trigger certain negative developments in the relationships. Developments like legal battles, arguments, hostilities, penalties, fines, etc come under the influence of the Seventh house. The way the person react to these developments also influences his relationship with other people. At the global level, these differences & misunderstandings between political leaders of different countries may even lead to armed conflicts and wars, in accordance with seventh house astrology.

The Seventh house is quite different from the First house (which is also known as Ascendant). The First house is self while the Seventh house is partner, thus they share an inextricable relationship. So, they complement each other and together create a whole. The Seventh house in Astrology refers to what a person is seeking or looking for. Everything related to marriage is governed by the Seventh house as per Seventh house astrology.

Benefits of having Seventh house in Twelve Zodiac Signs:

Seventh House posited in Aries:

If the seventh house is in Aries these persons are extremely passionate towards their partner and also in the work environment. Their anger is always on the top and they lose temper easily, thus it is important to have control over their anger. When it's come to the partner, they love to express their love and have a dominating behaviour over.

Seventh House posited in Taurus:

Natives with Taurus in the seventh house are intense and have a tendency of becoming too serious. In relationships, they always look for stability and seek a person who accomplishes them through their bad and good phase of life. When it comes to working, they are very concise and take their own space to complete their project.

Seventh House posited in Gemini:

Natives with this cusp believe in natural relationships and defy those who try to force commitment on them. At work, they are very delicate and jump from one project to another. Even something drops their task without completing it. For them communicating is the key to a successful relationship.

Seventh House posited in Cancer:

Natives with this cusp are sensible and a little emotional. Such people are deeply influenced by others and feel appreciated by them. In relationships, they always look for someone who is sensitive as well as understanding to them.

Seventh House posited in Leo:

Natives with this amalgamation are strong and bright, and they are very well aware of it. When it comes to relationships, natives are always looking for dominating personality. They love to support the weaker and use their own powerful energy to support the cause.

Seventh House posited in Virgo:

Natives with this cusp are always in look for someone who is down to earth. Someone who can complete them, and fill those empty parts that are lacking in relationships. People with the seventh house are detail-oriented and helpful who encourage others to follow their lead. Such people always succeed in professions related to education and mentorship.

Seventh House posited in Libra:

Natives with the cusp with the seventh house are mediators and search for a partner who is willing to discuss the hardship and differences. And look for a partner who shows the person the way to the middle ground. They are of kind nature and sometimes sensitive nature becomes the reason for their weakness.

Seventh House posited in Scorpio:

Natives with this cusp are very passionate and intense and find it difficult to acknowledge their strength and weakness, which becomes the reason for their messy relationship. However, when the person learns to accept the person's weakness, it becomes easier for the person to accept others. In relationships, such individuals are always looking for partners who are strong and powerful. The person believes in loyalty and expect the same from their partner.

Seventh House posited in Sagittarius:

Natives with this cusp are sociable and like meeting with people and as well as enjoy travelling. When it comes to relationships, such individuals always look for partners who have strong personalities and have diverse social lives. They hate clinginess and enjoy their alone time too. If they find a profession related to travelling, they enjoy it immensely.

Seventh House posited in Capricorn:

Natives with this cusp are very selective when it comes to finding the right partner. They set very high standards for others and look for someone who is loyal and supportive. Natives with Capricorn in Seventh House enjoy a good social status and want to be known for their skills and achievement.

Seventh House posited in Aquarius:

Natives with this cusp are very eccentric and incomprehensible by others. They are expressive and defying going with the other values. In a relationship, such individuals find partners who are independent and have strong personalities.

Seventh House posited in Pisces:

Natives with Pisces in the seventh house are looking for a partner who is sensitive and sweet. And be creative in nature. The person always loves being with someone who acknowledges others and accepts the person despite the person's weakness.

Nine Planets in the Seventh Bhava and their Significance and Effects:

Sun in Seventh House:

The Sun in the Seventh House will bring gain to the person from a marriage or business association. He will rise quickly up the ladder because he knows what he wants early on. The person will gain a status much higher than what he was born with. He will seek a partner of high status as well. This will give him a sense of security and even more confidence.

Natives born with the Sun in the seventh house are of great potential but they always rely on their partner to have success and make expected progression in life. Such individuals find it difficult to deal with problems and are very undecided in their thoughts.

Moon in Seventh House:

With Moon in the Seventh House, the person is likely to have a loving, compassionate and supportive partner. The person should control his moodiness, whether in marriage or business. The person looks for emotional security in a relationship. The Moon's influence indicates an enormous potential for compromise with partners and others in general.

Natives born with this sign are extremely blessed to have compassionate and loving partners. The person enjoys every aspect of life blissfully and have a tendency to be completely immersed with the person's partner. They are emotional and sensitive.

Mars in Seventh House:

Mars residing in the Seventh House suggests that the person's relationship will be a passionate and devoted one. The person looks for a partner who is active and courageous, someone who can stand shoulder-to-shoulder with him. The person like to do things in his own way and this could create problems in marriage or business. However, this placement can be good for business and career more than the marriage life.

Natives born with this sign are energetic and courageous and always be in shot-temperament most of the time. Native with Mars in the seventh house share every moment in their life and have a realistic expectation from their life partner.

Mercury in Seventh House:

Mercury residing in the Seventh house indicates that the person will have good communication with people in general. However, this placement can be problematic for romantic relationships because the person may not want to become committed. Mercury characteristics typically prefer enjoyment over hard work, commitment or consistency. However, the passage of time and life experiences will aid him in enjoying a more fulfilling relationship. The person should keep his dealings uncomplicated and honest.

Natives born with this sign are those who are intellectual and have a good sense of communication. Such people are very down-to-earth when it comes to maintaining their relationship, and this is the very reason why they enjoy a strong relationship with others.

Jupiter in Seventh House:

Jupiter positioned in the Seventh House will bring many opportunities to gain wealth through marriage or through a partner. This will make the person very optimistic. The person will have great expectations of others which will result in disappointments, especially if the person is a romantic partner. Nevertheless, this placement also creates happy partnerships and brings name and fame. In business, this placement will make the person aim high, but may also bring idealism into business matters.

Natives of this combination lives a very lucky and wealthy life. They are very intellectual and born to make startling discoveries. They are true humanitarian and believe in nurturing their relationship like a treasure

Venus in Seventh House:

With Venus in the Seventh House, the person will enjoy a good marriage. Marriage could also improve the person's financial and social status. This placement will give rise to romantic desires and longings. The person will want a beautiful partner with whom to enjoy the riches and comforts of life. The person should maintain a balanced attitude in love and not have high expectations with his partner.

Natives of this cusp are lucky and have a blissful relationship with their partner. And thus, both of them make a good bond with each other. Be it the moment of misery and blissfulness, they both are always together and help each other cope with it. These individuals enjoy music and drama greatly.

Saturn in Seventh House:

Saturn positioned in this house blesses the person with the most loyal and romantic partners. The person may fall for older or more mature partners. A partner who can stimulate the person to work hard will help the person to taste success, which is

what the person deeply desire. The person is likely to marry for emotional security rather than for love. At times the person may feel a lack of fulfilment in his personal relationship.

Natives of this Individual are loyal and faithful towards others. They are less talkative, but never ward off from standing against injustice. The person is such an individual who married with their own preferences of choice. When it comes to relationships, the person is very supportive and always be with each other in all thick and thin.

Rahu in Seventh House:

Rahu's presence in the Seventh House indicates a strong desire to be recognized as an equal in relationships and partnerships. The person has an emotional compulsion to be connected with others. Partners who are a bit eccentric or unusual, attract the person the most. Rahu in the Seventh House is not a strong indicator of faithfulness.

Ketu in Seventh House:

The person may witness hardships in his married life, especially concerning the health of his partner. Moreover, the person may suffer on the health front with him also. The person doesn't like the feeling of being defined by his partners. The person tends to become critical of partners or partnerships, preferring solitude and freedom to explore himself without the need to please anyone. This placement is equally unfavourable for business partnerships. The person may have to face conflicts with business partners or the partnership may not yield profits.

Each of the nine planets in Vedic astrology exists within a House (Bhava) in the birth chart (Rasi). Apart from providing invaluable insights about the person's personality, the placement of the planets illustrates how the person is connected and how the person coexists with the world around the person. Moreover the twelve houses in the horoscope of a person represent as a roadmap of that person's past, present and future. As the planets in the sky move across these houses, all sorts of events are triggered in the person's life both tangible and emotional.

Every house in the horoscope carries a unique meaning and represents a specific area of life. Indeed, the twelve houses are truly what makes astrology so spectacular. How these houses work is fairly complex, but now to make it easy for the person to understand what the Seventh house is explained here.

Seventh House and Marriage:

The Seventh House in the horoscope is connected to marriage. The planet that facilitates marriage is Venus. In everyone's horoscope, the list of auspicious planets includes Jupiter (Guru), Venus (Shukran), Mercury (Budhan) and Moon. The list of inauspicious planets includes Sun, Saturn (Sani), Mars (Sevvai), Rahu and Ketu. While auspicious planets cause early marriage, inauspicious planets cause delays in marriage.

If Mercury or Moon is posited in the Seventh House, the person will get married at a very young age between eighteen and Twenty three. If the Seventh House is occupied by Jupiter, the person will get married between Twenty four years and Twenty six years. Sun spotted in the Seventh House indicates the marriage shall be delayed and also faces a lot of obstacles. Mars in Seventh House is popularly known as Sevvai Dhosam, which causes serious delays in marriage. If Saturn sits in the Seventh House, then the person shall get married only after Thirty five years or even more.

Planetary Positions for Early Marriage:

When there are a greater number of benefice planets in the Seventh House, the person shall get married at a very young age between Sixteen and Twenty three years. For example, if Mercury and Venus jointly sit in the Seventh House, the person shall get married very soon. If one benefice planet is spotted in the Seventh House along with Saturn, then the marriage will get fixed at a very young age, but the marriage will happen only after two years.

Planetary Positions for Delay Marriage:

The reasons for late marriage in horoscope include planets like Sun, Saturn and Rahu. If any one of the planets including Sun, Saturn or Rahu is seen occupying the Seventh House, the marriage shall be delayed.

If there are no planets in the Seventh House, the marriage might take place early or late which will depend on the position of other planets in the birth chart.

Role of Jupiter in Fixing the Period of Marriage:

Astrology prediction for marriage can also tell when the person most likely to get married. Jupiter stays in a given zodiac sign for approximately twelve months and then moves the next one. Depending on the position of Jupiter in the horoscope, the marriage year can be predicted. While marriage is a crucial turn in life and it is natural that people might develop some anxiety regarding their marriage, studying the birth chart closely and gathering the necessary inputs from it can help to predict the time regarding marriage.

Conclusion:

Well, the seventh house differs from the first house (which is also known as Ascendant). The First house represents oneself, while the Seventh house represents one's partner, hence they are inextricably linked. As a result, they balance each other and work together to form a whole. In Astrology, the Seventh house represents what we are searching or looking for. According to Seventh house astrology, the Seventh house governs anything related to marriage.

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